

СРАВНЕНИЕ КУЛЬТУРНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ КИТАЯ И РОССИИ С ТОЧКИ ЗРЕНИЯ СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ

COMPARISON OF THE CULTURAL POLICY OF CHINA AND RUSSIA IN TERMS OF SOCIO-CULTURAL VALUES

ЛЮЙ ЧАО,

*аспирант кафедры культурологии и социально-культурной деятельности,
Уральский федеральный университет.*

КЕМЕРОВА ТАТЬЯНА АЛЕКСАНДРОВНА,

*кандидат философских наук,
доцент кафедры культурологии и социально-культурной деятельности,
Уральский федеральный университет.*

LV CHAO,

*post-graduate student of the department of culturology and socio-cultural activities,
Ural federal University.*

KEMEROVA TATIANA ALEXANDROVNA,

*PhD (Philosophy),
associate professor of the Department of Culturology and Socio-Cultural Activities,
Ural federal University.*

В статье анализируется и сравнивается культурная политика Китая и России, и делается вывод о том, что русская и китайская национальная культура является важной частью мировой культуры. Оба правительства защищают традиционное культурное наследие, укрепляют культурную мягкую силу, поддерживают национальную культурную безопасность и омолаживают нацию. Культурные устремления. В статье используются сравнительные методы для изучения национального опыта и национальных путей культурного развития России и Китая, анализируется географические и исторические причины их формирования, а также предлагаются полезные справочные материалы для двух стран при формулировании культурной политики.

The article analyzes and compares the cultural policies of China and Russia, and concludes that Russian and Chinese national culture are both important components of world culture. Both governments have the desire to protect traditional cultural heritage, enhance cultural soft power, maintain national cultural safe and revive national culture. The article uses comparative methods to study the national experience and the development of national culture in Russia and China, and analyzes the geographical and historical reasons for their formation. Provide a useful reference for the two countries to formulate cultural policies.

Ключевые слова: *китайская культура, русская культура, культурная политика, национальный дух, социальный менеджмент.*

Key words: *Chinese culture, Russian culture, cultural policy, national spirit, social management.*

Cultural policy is political propositions put forward by a country's ruling party and its government on some major issues in the development of art and culture. It is a concentrated expression of national will and core values in the cultural field. Both Russian national culture and Chinese national culture are outstanding in the world's cultural gardens. As two large countries on the Eurasian continent, both China and Russia have attached great importance to cultural construction in recent years. Through comparative research, we can understand the development of cultural policies between China and Russia, and then learn from each other.

Russia and China have very similar historical destinies and national cultural development paths in the 20th century. Since the mid-19th century, the development of the national culture of the two countries has experienced fierce disputes over whether to adhere to the traditional national culture or to westernize. In the context of globalization, both China and Russia are looking for their own development path amid social changes, and both hope to establish a new value system based on the national spiritual traditions, establish a new mainstream cultural spirit, and complete social cultural transformation. Therefore, it is of great significance to compare the cultural policies of China and Russia.

At the beginning of the 21st century, President Putin put forward the national concept of "New Russian Thought", and the Russian government implemented the national strategy of "rebuilding the image of a great power." Cultural governance has always been an important way to revitalize Russia. [1, C. 50] Contemporary Russia attaches so much importance to governing national cultural undertakings and cultural activities through laws or regulations and national policies, which is closely related to the tradition of the Russian nation. In history, the formation of Russian aristocracy and the course of the tsarist monarchy determined the basic way of top-down Russian social governance. The characteristic of contemporary Russian social governance is that since 2000, Russia has formed a political structure with the president as the core of decision-making, the federal parliament as the legislative body, and the federal government and its subordinate departments as the executive body. In the field of culture, the President directly proposes to study and determine the basic principles of national cultural policies and implement them by government departments. First of all various cultural policies will be implemented mainly through the formulation of the outline of the cultural project planning of the Russian Federation. In specific practice, the President elaborated on the basic principles of cultural policy through the State of the Union address, presidential decree, and important speeches. For example, President Putin said at the Congress of the Writers Association: "The protection of our (Russian) language, literature and culture is a national security issue, and is the core of maintaining our identity under the conditions of globalization." [2, C. 112] The president can sign the Federal Constitution and Federal laws or write rejections of federal laws express a principled position on national cultural policy issues.

China's cultural management method is also dominated by the central government, and its role has undergone a change from "hosting culture" to "managing culture". Since China's social environment and social nature are different from Western countries, and the development path of cultural industries is also very different, China's cultural policies need to be formulated and implemented by the government. [3] However, with the promulgation of the "Decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on Deepening Reform" in November 2013, the government gradually changed its functions and proposed for the first time that "the market plays a decisive role in the allocation of resources" and "the establishment of a sound modern cultural market system". Over the past few years, the central government has actively promoted and promoted market-oriented reforms, adjusted cultural industry policies, reduced direct government intervention in resources, and promoted resource allocation in accordance with market rules, market prices, and market competition. The effect of the transformation from the government's own organizational culture to management culture is obvious. [4] This also shows that China is exploring a cultural development model based on law, guided by policies, and supported by a modern cultural market system.

The management method of "legalized management" is also gradually being carried out, and cultural legislation is receiving more and more attention. For example, in 2015, China's museum industry's first national regulatory document "Museum Regulations" was formally implemented, using institutional guarantees to promote the standardized and professional development of museum undertakings. In addition, the first basic law in the cultural field «Public Cultural Service Guarantee Law», came into force on March 1, 2017. It provides a more powerful legal basis and system guarantee for promoting the standardization and equalization of basic public cultural services. It can be seen from the above that cultural legislation is an important means for China and Russia to protect the basic cultural rights and interests of citizens in cultural construction.

In addition, China and Russia have introduced relevant cultural policies in order to break the imbalance in regional, city and countryside cultural development and investment. Russia promulgated the "Russian National Cultural Policy Foundation" in 2014, proposing to "form a cultural service system with no difference in social status, no difference in ethnic attributes, no difference in religious beliefs, and no regional difference, covering all Russian citizens. It will be a high-quality cultural service system. , Socialized and free of charge. Enable citizens to enjoy cultural values and the right to participate in cultural activities, and pay attention to regional and social equality." [5] As an important principle for the development of Russian culture in the future, special emphasis is placed on "The unification of the cultural space of the Russian Federation is the foundation of national security and integrity, including rural areas." In particular increased the "Golden Classic of Russian Songs" Traditional Folk Song Art Festival, the "Highland" Folklore International Festival, the "Russian Craftsman" All-Russian Folk Artists, the "Golden Ring" Folk Craft International Festival, and the "Russian Matryoshka" Traditional Folk Culture Art festivals and other 26 rural cultural promotion activities involving folk music, folk literature, and traditional handicrafts, so as to promote the development of ordinary people's cultural life and the equality of cultural rights.

The State Council of China promulgated the "Opinions on Establishing a System and Policy System for Urban and Rural Integrated Development" on April 15, 2019. Article 15 of it states: Should build a public cultural service system in urban and rural areas, promote the popularization of cultural resources in rural areas, and improve the coverage of services promotes the effective connection between cultural projects and residents' needs. Support rural folk cultural groups to carry out cultural activities in line with rural characteristics. Establish a cultural assistance system to encourage cultural workers and volunteers to devote themselves to rural cultural construction. Establish a rural historical and cultural protection law to protect agricultural cultural relics, ethnic villages, and traditional architectural heritage, and promote the inheritance of intangible cultural heritage. [6] It can be seen the government attaches great importance to the important role of excellent traditional culture. During 2018-2020, the Ministry of Culture has promulgated a total of 175 "Hometowns of Chinese Folk Culture and Art". Its purpose is to activate mass cultural activities and promote the construction of a public cultural service system. By exploring folk cultural resources, promote the cultural consciousness of the grassroots people, and ensure that the grassroots people have equal opportunities to participate in cultural activities, engage in cultural creation, and enjoy cultural services. Therefore, the primary feature of the "Hometown of Chinese Folk Culture and Art" is its popularity and mass participation.

According to Decree No. 80 of the State Council of China (2018), starting from 2018, the "Chinese Farmers Harvest Festival" will be established every autumn equinox. The establishment of the "Harvest Festival" will greatly arouse the enthusiasm and creativity of Chinese farmers. Enhance the sense of honor and happiness of hundreds of millions of farmers. Holding the "Chinese Farmers Harvest Festival" can show China's agriculture-oriented tradition since ancient times and has important cultural significance. From a historical perspective, rural culture is extensive and profound, including historical celebrities, historical allusions, characteristic buildings, characteristic food, and intangible cultural heritage. The purpose of setting up the Harvest Festival is to fully ex-

cavate these cultural relics and make them play a role in the implementation of the rural revitalization strategy.

From the legal content of the above two countries, it can be seen both countries attach great importance to the balanced development of urban and rural cultural services, so as to protect the cultural rights of all citizens. The peasant issue is the most important social issue in the history of China and Russia. Both countries put the focus of social governance on the peasants who account of majority of the social population. Cultural and social governance has important practical relevance and governance strategies. Perfect cultural laws, regulations and literary policies are of great significance to how to solve the problems of uneven cultural development and loss of folk cultural heritage caused by the vast land area, numerous ethnic groups, and uneven populations in China and Russia. [7, C. 50]

In summary, it can be seen the efforts made by China and Russia to share cultural public resources and equal life and development for all people reflect the common social and cultural values. The cultural laws and policies of the two countries have distinct characteristics of "nationalization": First, the basic national value spirit with "patriotism", "power awareness" and "social unity" as the core is different from the individualistic social value orientation. The second is based on the principle of "sovereign democracy" in which the state leads cultural leadership, controls cultural language rights, guarantees the rights of Chinese and Russian citizens in cultural activities, and protects national cultural heritage and national cultural characteristics. The third is to emphasize the essential link between national cultural security and national unity. The characteristics of these cultural policies are determined by the historical and cultural characteristics of the two countries that are different from other countries. Both China and Russia hope to consolidate national spirit, shape national image, and enhance cultural soft power. The mutual reference in cultural policies between China and Russia is of positive significance for enhancing cultural exchanges between the two countries and promoting mutual understanding of national conditions, values, and cultural policies between two countries.

REFERENCES

1. Zhang Zhengwen. The Historical Perspective of Russian Cultural Policy in Putin's Period // Eastern Europe and Central Asia Studies. – 2017. – №1. – С. 39-51.
2. Qi Shuyu. Chinese Cultural Policy Research Report // Social Science Literature Press. –2011.–432с.
3. Policy review and trend orientation in China's cultural industry since the 18th National Congress – [Electronic resource]–Access mode: https://www.sohu.com/a/197903415_645125
4. Conclusion of the State Council on the creation and improvement of the system, mechanism and policy system for the development of urban and rural integration– [Electronic resource]–Access mode: http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/2019-05/05/content_5388880.htm
5. Meeting of the Russian literature and language society – [Electronic resource]–Access mode: <http://en.kremlin.ru/catalog/keywords/81/events/52007>
6. Zhang Ping. Putin's view of Russian culture // Academic Exploration. – 2014. – №2. – С. 110-114.
7. Zhen Wendong. Cultural Security and the Rise and Fall of Great Powers: The Enlightenment of Russia's Cultural Security Strategy to China // Asia-Africa Aspects. – 2013. – №6. – С. 44-51.

© Lv Chao, Kemerova T.A., 2021.